

EMVA 1288 Data Sheet m0728

This datasheet describes the specification according to the standard 1288 for “Characterization and Presentation of Specification Data for Image Sensors and Cameras of the European Machine Vision Association (EMVA)” (see www.standard1288.org or the *Zenodo EMVA 1288 community*) release 3.0 with proprietary extensions from AEON. The measurements were performed with the AEON ACC2b RGB-IR, Release 5, 27.06.2014, SN 0009(HCI) . The performance parameters and estimated accuracy of the measurements are described in the technical report for the instrument, its calibration in the corresponding specification and calibration report.

Measurements performed by B Jähne, HCI, Heidelberg University and H Herrmann, AEON

Vendor	Basler
Model	acA1920-155um
Serial number	21735903
Sensor diagonal	13.40 mm
Lens category	C-mount
Resolution	1936 × 1216, 12 bit
Pixel size	5.86 μm × 5.86 μm
Sensor	Sony IMX174
Sensor type	CMOS
Shutter type	Global
Overlap capabilities	Overlapping
Maximum frame rate	76.3 Hz
Interface type	USB3 Vision

Type of data presented	Single
Operation point 1, (page 5)	
Wavelength centroid	465.8 nm
Wavelength FWHM	20.9 nm
Gain, offset	12.0 dB, 10 DN
Operation point 2, (page 20)	
Wavelength centroid	533.9 nm
Wavelength FWHM	31.3 nm
Gain, offset	12.0 dB, 10 DN
Operation point 3, (page 35)	
Wavelength centroid	630.1 nm
Wavelength FWHM	13.2 nm
Gain, offset	12.0 dB, 10 DN
Optional data measured	
None	

Spectral sensitivity m0727, 19.08.2015

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 1

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	12.0 dB, 10 DN
Exposure control	by irradiance	Environmental temperature	24.4°C
Exposure time	250.00 μ s	Camera body temperature	36.1°C
Frame rate	76.3 Hz	Intern temperature(s)	—
Data transfer mode	Mono 12	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	466 nm, 20.9 nm

Quantum efficiency

η 70.9%

Overall system gain

K 0.501 DN/e
 $1/K$ 1.995 e /DN

Temporal dark noise & DSNU

$\sigma_{y, \text{dark}}$ 2.23 DN
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.41 DN
 σ_d 4.41 e
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.81 e

Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU

SNR_{max} 89
39.0 dB
6.5 bit
 $1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ 1.13 %
PRNU₁₂₈₈ 0.47 %

Nonlinearity

LE 0.13%
LE_{min} -0.12%
LE_{max} 0.14%

Sensitivity & saturation

$\mu_{p, \text{min}}$ 7.01 p
0.204 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{p, \text{sat}}$ 11084 p
323 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{min}}$ 4.97 e
0.145 e / μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{sat}}$ 7863 e
229 e / μm^2

Dynamic range

DR 1582
64.0 dB
10.6 bit

Dark current

$\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ 2.8 DN/s
 $\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ 5.6 e /s
 $\mu_{c, \text{var}}$ 5.6 e /s

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 2

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	12.0 dB, 10 DN
Exposure control	by irradiance	Environmental temperature	24.4°C
Exposure time	250.00 μ s	Camera body temperature	36.1°C
Frame rate	76.3 Hz	Intern temperature(s)	—
Data transfer mode	Mono 12	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	534 nm, 31.3 nm

Photon transfer m0728, 534 nm, 20.08.2015

SNR m0728, 534 nm, 20.08.2015

Quantum efficiency

η 67.1%

Overall system gain

K 0.501 DN/e
 $1/K$ 1.996 e /DN

Temporal dark noise & DSNU

$\sigma_{y, \text{dark}}$ 2.23 DN
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.41 DN
 σ_d 4.41 e
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.82 e

Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU

SNR_{max} 88
38.9 dB
6.5 bit
 $1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ 1.13 %
PRNU₁₂₈₈ 0.47 %

Nonlinearity

LE 0.15%
LE_{min} -0.11%
LE_{max} 0.19%

Sensitivity & saturation

$\mu_{p, \text{min}}$ 7.42 p
0.216 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{p, \text{sat}}$ 11658 p
339 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{min}}$ 4.98 e
0.145 e / μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{sat}}$ 7818 e
228 e / μm^2

Dynamic range

DR 1571
63.9 dB
10.6 bit

Dark current

$\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — DN/s
 $\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — e /s
 $\mu_{c, \text{var}}$ — e /s

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 3

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	12.0 dB, 10 DN
Exposure control	by irradiance	Environmental temperature	24.4°C
Exposure time	250.00 μ s	Camera body temperature	36.1°C
Frame rate	76.3 Hz	Intern temperature(s)	—
Data transfer mode	Mono 12	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	630 nm, 13.2 nm

Photon transfer m0728, 630 nm, 20.08.2015

SNR m0728, 630 nm, 20.08.2015

Quantum efficiency

η 49.2%

Overall system gain

K 0.501 DN/e
 $1/K$ 1.996 e /DN

Temporal dark noise & DSNU

$\sigma_{y,dark}$ 2.22 DN
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.41 DN
 σ_d 4.39 e
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.82 e

Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU

SNR_{max} 89
39.0 dB
6.5 bit
 $1/\text{SNR}_{max}$ 1.13 %
PRNU₁₂₈₈ 0.48 %

Nonlinearity

LE 0.15%
LE_{min} -0.13%
LE_{max} 0.17%

Sensitivity & saturation

$\mu_{p,min}$ 10.07 p
0.293 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{p,sat}$ 15991 p
466 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{e,min}$ 4.96 e
0.144 e / μm^2
 $\mu_{e,sat}$ 7874 e
229 e / μm^2

Dynamic range

DR 1588
64.0 dB
10.6 bit

Dark current

$\mu_{c,mean}$ — DN/s
 $\mu_{c,mean}$ — e /s
 $\mu_{c,var}$ — e /s

Detailed Data Operating Point 1, 466 nm

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1.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.050	0.051	0.050	0.050	0.051	0.050	0.050	0.050
0.026	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.026	0.026
0.002	0.002	0.002	0.003	0.001	0.003	0.002	0.004	0.003
0.000	0.001	0.002	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.003	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.002
0.005	0.005	0.004	0.003	0.006	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.004
0.002	0.002	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.001
0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001
0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001
0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001
0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.002

1.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

1.3 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

1.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

SNR m0728, 466 nm, 20.08.2015

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

1.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 10.0 - 12.5 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.10 DN.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.10 DN.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 1.4\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0728, 466 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.070%.

Vertical spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0728, 466 nm, 20.08.2015

Vertical spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.070%.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0728, 466 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal lines PRNU m0728, 466 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical lines DSNU m0728, 466 nm, 20.08.2015

Vertical lines PRNU m0728, 466 nm, 20.08.2015

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Horizontal profiles residual PRNU (in extension to EMVA 1288)

Residual PRNU m0728, 466 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal profiles of residual PRNU for middle line in % of mean after two-point calibration with dark image and 50% saturation image for a low and high saturation level.

Table with residual inhomogeneities at different saturation levels after a two-point correction with dark image and 50% saturation image.

Saturation %	μ_y DN	σ_y DN	s_y DN	$\sigma_{y.res}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ %	$s_{y.corr}/s_y$ %
0	11.24	2.22	0.41	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	393.93	14.16	2.00	0.63	0.94	0.24	47.13
20	785.09	20.07	3.77	0.89	1.18	0.15	31.18
30	1194.61	24.68	5.79	1.09	1.44	0.12	24.85
40	1579.39	28.28	7.59	1.25	1.73	0.11	22.87
50	1983.81	31.51	9.26	1.39	0.05	0.00	0.53
60	2383.03	34.44	10.79	1.52	2.47	0.10	22.93
70	2757.75	37.18	12.30	1.64	3.35	0.12	27.27
80	3169.66	39.73	13.97	1.76	4.26	0.13	30.47
90	3561.25	42.61	15.84	1.88	4.72	0.13	29.79
100	3950.09	44.81	17.60	1.98	4.82	0.12	27.38

Detailed Data Operating Point 2, 534 nm

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2.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.051	0.050	0.050	0.049	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.050
0.025	0.024	0.024	0.025	0.024	0.024	0.024	0.026	0.024
0.001	0.001	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002
0.002	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.002	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.002	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.002	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.003	0.001
0.003	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.004	0.002	0.003

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001
0.001	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000
0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.000
0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001

2.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

2.3 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

2.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

SNR m0728, 534 nm, 20.08.2015

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

2.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 10.0 - 12.5 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.10 DN.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.10 DN.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 1.4\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0728, 534 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.071%.

Vertical spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0728, 534 nm, 20.08.2015

Vertical spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.071%.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0728, 534 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal lines PRNU m0728, 534 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical lines DSNU m0728, 534 nm, 20.08.2015

Vertical lines PRNU m0728, 534 nm, 20.08.2015

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Horizontal profiles residual PRNU (in extension to EMVA 1288)

Residual PRNU m0728, 534 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal profiles of residual PRNU for middle line in % of mean after two-point calibration with dark image and 50% saturation image for a low and high saturation level.

Table with residual inhomogeneities at different saturation levels after a two-point correction with dark image and 50% saturation image.

Saturation %	μ_y DN	σ_y DN	s_y DN	$\sigma_{y.res}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ %	$s_{y.corr}/s_y$ %
0	11.25	2.22	0.41	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	386.16	14.03	2.04	0.62	0.95	0.25	46.37
20	788.03	20.10	3.88	0.89	1.19	0.15	30.69
30	1176.19	24.49	5.79	1.08	1.43	0.12	24.61
40	1566.42	28.15	7.63	1.24	1.72	0.11	22.60
50	1961.86	31.32	9.27	1.38	0.03	0.00	0.29
60	2364.26	34.31	10.83	1.52	2.46	0.10	22.73
70	2753.33	37.14	12.40	1.64	3.39	0.12	27.32
80	3155.62	39.61	14.02	1.75	4.29	0.14	30.59
90	3543.91	42.49	15.82	1.88	4.78	0.13	30.20
100	3948.86	44.80	17.65	1.98	4.91	0.12	27.80

Detailed Data Operating Point 3, 630 nm

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3.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.042	0.042	0.041	0.042	0.042	0.042	0.042	0.042
0.022	0.022	0.023	0.022	0.022	0.023	0.022	0.023	0.023
0.005	0.004	0.005	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.004	0.005
0.002	0.000	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.002
0.001	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.000
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.000	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000
0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000
0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000
0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000
0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000
0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

3.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

3.3 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

3.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

SNR m0728, 630 nm, 20.08.2015

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

3.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 10.0 - 12.5 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.10 DN.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.10 DN.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 1.4\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0728, 630 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.070%.

Vertical spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0728, 630 nm, 20.08.2015

Vertical spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.070%.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0728, 630 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal lines PRNU m0728, 630 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical lines DSNU m0728, 630 nm, 20.08.2015

Vertical lines PRNU m0728, 630 nm, 20.08.2015

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Horizontal profiles residual PRNU (in extension to EMVA 1288)

Residual PRNU m0728, 630 nm, 20.08.2015

Horizontal profiles of residual PRNU for middle line in % of mean after two-point calibration with dark image and 50% saturation image for a low and high saturation level.

Table with residual inhomogeneities at different saturation levels after a two-point correction with dark image and 50% saturation image.

Saturation %	μ_y DN	σ_y DN	s_y DN	$\sigma_{y.res}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ %	$s_{y.corr}/s_y$ %
0	11.24	2.22	0.41	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	393.12	14.15	2.02	0.63	0.95	0.25	46.84
20	798.48	20.24	3.91	0.89	1.19	0.15	30.40
30	1190.27	24.63	5.87	1.09	1.44	0.12	24.53
40	1591.58	28.39	7.78	1.25	1.75	0.11	22.44
50	1992.03	31.58	9.45	1.40	0.00	0.00	0.02
60	2366.54	34.34	10.91	1.52	2.43	0.10	22.30
70	2771.07	37.28	12.57	1.65	3.38	0.12	26.86
80	3151.54	39.60	14.10	1.75	4.21	0.13	29.87
90	3559.23	42.62	16.08	1.88	4.71	0.13	29.28
100	3944.40	44.84	17.82	1.98	4.82	0.12	27.02

Comparative Evaluation with all Colors

This whole section is in extension to the EMVA 1288 standard.

Comparative characteristic curve for selected colors/channels as indicated in the legend.

Comparative photon transfer curve for all measured color/channel combinations.

Comparative double-logarithmic SNR curve for selected colors/channels as indicated in the legend.

Residual color PRNU m0728, 20.08.2015

Color dependency of PRNU: profile of middle row of sensor, shown as deviation from PRNU averaged over all measured colors.

Dark Current

Dark current from mean m0728, 20.08.2015

Mean of dark signal versus exposure time.

Dark current from variance m0728, 20.08.2015

Variance of dark signal versus exposure time.

Spatial variation of dark current (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of dark current in e^-/s from mean values

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of dark current in e^-/s from variance

Comments